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**PHÁT TRIỂN NÔNG NGHIỆP BỀN VỮNG Ở VIỆT NAM
KINH NGHIỆM CÁC QUỐC GIA CHÂU Á**

**SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN VIETNAM
EXPERIENCE OF ASIAN COUNTRIES**

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SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN VIETNAM - EXPERIENCE OF ASIAN COUNTRIES

SÁCH KHÔNG BÁN

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July, 2020
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

NHÀ XUẤT BẢN
ĐẠI HỌC QUỐC GIA TP. HỒ CHÍ MINH

A MESSAGE FROM THE RECTOR OF UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS
AND LAW, VIETNAM NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF HO CHI MINH
CITY

On behalf of the University of Economics and Law (UEL), Vietnam National University of Ho Chi Minh City (VNU-HCM), I am honored to welcome all of you to participate in the 2020 International Conference on Sustainable Agricultural Development in Vietnam – Experience of Asian Countries (SADVN 2020).

Agriculture plays a strategic role in the process of economic development of a country. There are many issues involving sustainable agricultural development that have to be addressed to increase the quality of life in developing countries as targeted by Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): poverty and hunger, climate change, energy, consumption, marine resources, inequality, economic growth, ecosystems and environment, food security, social justice, industrial sustainability, good health and inclusive well-being, accountable and inclusive institutions, and the global partnership for sustainable development. It is also within this context that we are very privileged to hold the SADVN 2020 conference at the University of Economics and Law campus – No. 669, Quarter 3, Linh Xuan Ward, Thu Duc District, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam on July 17th, 2020, together with Economists Club (Ho Chi Minh City Union of Business Association), Department of Science and Technology of Ho Chi Minh City, and Universitas Islam Indonesia.

In this conference, leading scholars, researchers, and practitioners from Vietnam and other Asian countries present their papers on how effective the role of sustainable agricultural development is in each country. These studies also propose best practices, policies, and strategies for sustainable agricultural development in Vietnam and Asian countries such as high-tech agriculture, green agriculture, smart agriculture, sustainable supply chains of agri-food, farmland policies, agricultural production system, agribusiness, agricultural labor, digital transformation in agriculture, and technology adoption in agricultural sustainability. These precious recommendations will be the foundation for implementing sustainable agricultural development policies for Vietnam.

We are delighted to receive much attention with over 65 papers written by authors from Taiwan, India, Indonesia, Thailand, Philippines, Cambodia, and Vietnam. All manuscripts submitted to SADVN 2020 conference underwent a rigorous peer-review process from the editorial committee to ensure high quality in accepted papers. For SADVN 2020, 51 papers were selected for presentation at the symposium and inclusion in the conference proceedings with International Standard Book Number (ISBN).

This year, in the context of the COVID-19 outbreaks across many countries, we totally understand the safety concerns and travel restrictions. Therefore, we decided to offer two ways: online and traditional presentation in the SADVN 2020 conference. We hope that despite these difficulties, all of you will enjoy fruitful discussions during the conference and

develop new friendships and collaborations among participants and institutions.

We are very grateful to the Vietnam National University of Ho Chi Minh City for giving us this opportunity to organize the SADVN 2020 conference. We would like to take this opportunity to say a special thank you to the Department of Science and Technology of Ho Chi Minh City, and Economists Club (Ho Chi Minh City Union of Business Association) for your generous donations and supports to this conference. Our thanks also go to the scholars from Taiwan, Thailand, Philippines, and Indonesia who accepted to be with us by online presentations during the novel COVID-19 pandemic. We sincerely appreciate managers and policymakers for their great contributions and to all Organizing Committee members for providing timely and in-depth reviews. Last but not least, we would like to thank the scholars from various parts of Vietnam for their attendance and presentation at the conference in spite of the COVID-19 pandemic. I am beyond grateful to welcome you here at this conference, and may we have a fun yet meaningful discourse at this conference! I wish all of you good health, successes, and prosperity in the future.

Prof. Dr. Nguyen Tien Dzung
Rector of UEL, VNU-HCM

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ĐỂ CÓ SÁCH HAY, CẦN CHUNG TAY BẢO VỆ TÁC QUYỀN!

SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT OF MARKET MOBILE APPLICATION FOR SUSTAINABLE LOCAL INDUSTRY IN THE PHILIPPINES

Analiza V. Muñoz¹

Abstract

The Philippines is abundant in natural resources, including a broad variety of locally produced goods and raw materials. These goods have been extracted from the natural environment by the primary sector for the consumption and use of the people living in the Philippines or by converting these raw materials into new products for sale or export to other countries by the secondary sector, while a tertiary sector provides its customers with services. The primary sector is the backbone of social and economic growth and supports the stability of the Philippines in the production of agricultural, fisheries, forestry and mining products, all of which are derived from the natural environment and the main component of all other products and foods used and consumed by the people.

Although the primary sector plays an important role in the economic activity and growth of the Philippines as it supplies basic food and raw materials to other sectors, it is still considered to be the poorest of the poor based on the 2020 Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) report. The largest incidences of poverty among the core sectors were recorded in 2018 in 31.6, 26.2, 24.5 and 23.9 percent of farmers, fishermen, rural residents, and children belonging to families below the official poverty rate, respectively. These sectors also report 40.8, 36.9, 34.0 and 33.5% of the highest levels of poverty in 2015 (PSA 2020). The researcher conducted this study to develop the Market Mobile Application (M-Mobile App), a software for mobile devices such as mobile phones, smartphones, personal digital assistants (PDA), tablets, or other mobile equipment to directly connect from the primary sector (the seller) to the people (consumer). This will provide innovative methods for the primary sector to improve their livelihoods and develop their skills and knowledge by using mobile technology as a medium to increase their economic activity and eventually transforming them into entrepreneurs and business owners. This research will also highlight the economic activity involved, the sales transaction from the Primary Sector to Consumer (Ps2C) through a mobile application.

In this study, a mixed research methodology of quantitative and qualitative data was used through a structured survey questionnaire in the Point Four Likert Scale, Literature Review and Scoping Review Method. The results will be interpreted using a Triangulation Analysis by analyzing the results of the survey questionnaire using simple frequency

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distribution and a review of several kinds of research and publications. The researcher has decided to develop a mobile application for the primary sector to improve their living conditions. In documenting the results of the research based on the review, the data collected from the literature were grouped into subjects corresponding to the answers to the research questions. The Scoping Review Method was used to determine, prioritize, associate and identify gaps and/or priorities of the primary sector.

Keywords: *Local Industries, Mobile Application, Sustainable, E-Commerce, Primary Sector*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is an archipelago country consisting of 7,107 islands covering 300,000 square kilometers (USAID, 2011) or approximately 30 million hectares (FMB, 2017). It is rich in natural and mineral (metallic and non-metallic) resources (ECCP, 2019), which is a valuable asset that contributes to the country's national wealth. It is a major source of income and livelihood for the Filipino people. The continuous improvement of these resources is significant for the country's stable economic systems, where the government will have an impact on their productivity through the successful implementation of a sustainable economic and social development framework and protection for small local industries and the primary sector.

Primary industries or sectors of the economy are directly dependent on the environment or natural resources, such as land, forests, water, plants, materials for construction, and minerals (NSCB, 1998). They supply raw materials to the secondary industry/sector for conversion to another product for customer or consumer used and consumption. Also, the primary sector is classified as "the extractive sector," they perform agricultural and harvesting activities, crop production, fishing, forestry, hunting, domesticated animals and livestock breeding, and mining & quarrying. People involved in these primary activities are often referred to as the "red-collar workers or extractive workers" due to the outdoor aspect of their work and activities (George, 2020).

This sector may seem to have sufficient resources for a stable and comfortable life, as the raw materials it sells come from the environment. The researchers found, however, that it makes no logical conclusion that the primary industry would lead a pleasant or elegant life through the perceived availability of natural resources. In fact, they are among the poorest of the poor (PSA, 2020). The situation is further compounded by the younger generation, which largely decides to leave rural areas nationwide due to poverty, the depletion of a number of potential domestic workers or future primary sectors, not to mention other factors that worsen the scenario, such as changes in ecosystems and climate change that affect the productivity of the primary sector.

The welfare of primary sectors, such as farmers, fishermen, skilled craftsmen, animal breeders and miners in developing countries, depends heavily on the selling price of their products or the value of raw materials sold (Jensen, 2007). From a bargaining point of view,

information asymmetries on prevailing market prices between primary sectors and traders are highly detrimental to the welfare of the primary sector and it appears that the products or raw materials purchased from them by traders are so low and then sold by traders at a higher price.

On the other hand, if the product or raw materials are sold directly from the primary sector to consumer (Ps2C), the decision to change the price belongs to the primary sector, either to sell the products at the current market price or to sell them at a lower price. This direct market transaction/activity will help the primary sector to make more profits and encourage them to make more products available to meet customers' changing needs.

Public administration, therefore, performs an important role in helping the primary sector to change its old practices and behaviour, as well as its indigenous reasoning, especially in the younger generation. The public administration should give them a better opportunity to experience the benefits of innovation and technology for sustainable natural resources, to develop sound policies on agriculture, fisheries, mining, forestry and animal breeding, and to promote a learning atmosphere for the primary sector and their children to enhance their skills and knowledge in this new mobile technology.

The increasing demand for mobile access enables the researcher to use the mobile application technology as the focus of the study. It aims to support the primary sector by developing a mobile application called Market Mobile Application (M-Mobile App). This will provide them not only a channel for direct market transactions between the primary sector and consumer but also with immediate access to government resources, projects and initiatives, legislation and regulations relevant to their work, climate/weather forecasting or information, communication chat box, and best practices data. It also creates an opportunity for collaborations, and promotes partnership between the private sector, civil society, and government sectors. Mobile apps are somewhat different from those designed for PCs and laptops because the users have different needs and expectations (Gonzalez, 2001), and apps installed on mobile phone devices can be used anywhere and can be accessed at any time as they are user-friendly and cost-effective. The M-Mobile application was therefore developed to address the needs, expectations and important information needed by the primary sector in the conduct of their work and daily activities.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the potential impact on people using mobile applications in the purchase of goods and other day-to-day needs by assessing and analyzing variety of published and unpublished works, articles, and other information.
2. To provide the government with an alternative way of supporting the primary sector by offering it a revolutionary method of improving market activity.
3. Present the mobile device application that will provide the primary sector with a knowledge-based handy device as well as an innovative channel for economic activity.

Theoretical Framework

Mobile phone apps can be a valuable resource for presenting accurate and reliable information to the primary sector and their families on essential decision-making strategies for planting, fisheries, forestry, mining and livestock breeding, and for creating a convenient channel to connect directly between the primary sector and consumers in the conduct of purchase decisions, financial transactions and marketing activities. While the evolution of mobile developments promotes m-commerce with a potential means for massive growth in digital interface transactions, m-commerce activities between sellers and consumers continue to expand (Sadi & Noordin, 2011).

Past studies have taken advantage of Mobile Technology Theory and the Rural Technology Acceptance Model (Islam & Ake, 2011), Expectance-Value Motivational theory, 'Digital-Divide' concept (Chisama, 2016), Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989), Perceived Ease of Use or User-Friendliness Theory (Newman, et al., 2018), among others.

The researcher has adopted the Expectancy-Value Motivational Theory (EVMT) and the Digital-Divide Framework. The EVMT postulates that the motivation for a particular potential outcome is measured in two ways: 1) the expectancy, which is considered as the probability to obtain the desired (instrumental) outcome of the person through actions or decision; and 2) the value, which is the ideal result expected by the person as an outcome (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002). Such two key factors are associated with multiplication, for example, motivation = expectation x value. Both expectations and values have a significant impact on determining the future actions, commitment, resilience and success of the individual in the context of the Expectancy-Value Motivation theory.

In this research, the primary sector expects the development of M-Mobile Application to help them market their domestic product, to provide them with all the information they need, such as news, weather conditions and training to improve productivity. They expect to use it in a convenient and user-friendly manner. If the use of this mobile application provides convenience and exceeds the user's expectations, it is likely that the primary sector will continue to use the application and will recommend its use to others. Likewise, if the customer finds this mobile application user-friendly, convenient, easy-to-use and timely, they are likely to use the app and recommend it to others. If both the primary sector and the consumer have a positive experience of using a mobile application, they will both be motivated to use it, explore the other features of the application, and recommend innovation to meet their changing needs and expectation for marketing or e-commerce applications.

The researcher also used the Digital Divide framework in this study, the term "digital divide" was presented in the mid-1990s and described as the disparity between those who have access to the latest information or communication system tools and technology and those who do not have access (Van Dijk, 2006). The digital divide remains an important public policy controversy covering political, social and economic issues (Srinuan et al., 2011). In the current research, the primary sectors, most of which live in remote areas, where access to the Internet is usually impossible, but with emerging mobile technologies,

the primary sector has been able to use mobile phones to communicate with friends and their loved ones who are far from them. This technology enables the primary sector not only to use their mobile phones for communication, but also to help them earn a living.

This innovation should result in a shift from the traditional business transaction where the primary sector sells its product to traders and the latter sells it to consumers/customers to technology-based business transaction. The use of mobile applications will reduce the sales process where the primary sector sells its products directly to the consumer (Ps2C) in order to bridge the gap between people living in remote provinces, where most of the primary sector lives, and connect with the urban community where most consumers reside.

Public administration has a key position to make this innovation happen and to make changes in resources such as mobile phones or smartphones available for market activities. Changing resources to include mobile phones and internet access for the primary sector or those living in remote areas. The public administration should provide the primary sector with the way to enable them to purchase mobile phones suitable for downloading of application and access to the Internet. The resources they need also include training opportunities for mobile technology. This will help the primary sector to develop its skills and awareness of the use and operation of mobile phones for mobile market-based activities.

The Public administration may also initiate a new mechanism for collaboration with civil society and partnerships with the private sector, such as telecommunication providers. All mobile phone companies have offered internet connections but still need loads to support internet surfing subscription. In this digital divide framework, material access (the ability to purchase mobile phones) is preceded by motivational access (communication and business transactions), followed by skills access (use of mobile phone technology) and usage access (internet) (Van Dijk, 2006). In order to avoid the gap caused by the digital divide, these factors as shown in Figure 1 should be considered by the public administration.

Figure 1. A cumulative and recursive method of successive kinds of access to digital technologies

Source: van Dijk (2005)

The literature review shows that the digital divide as shown in Figure 1 is apparently due to the assessment of gaps in physical access to computer hardware, laptops and other electronic devices (material access) and the use of internet (skills access) between demographic characteristics (user access) in terms of sex, age, education, income and ethnicity. The main consequence of the digital divide is the participation and involvement of the most specific aspects of society (politics, economy, social institutions, geographic mobility, culture, social networks and communities) (Van Dijk, 2006).

Apart from the physical distance of intended users, mobile phone features and capacity also create a gap in the use of mobile technology, because most of the primary sector did not complete formal education and was considered to be the poorest of the poor. Consequently, they do not have the means to purchase a mobile phone that can be used for mobile applications and the right skills to operate the installation and use of mobile applications, which are worsened by no access to the Internet at their remote location. These gaps can be properly addressed by the public administration in partnership with telecommunications companies, by providing signals to remote areas where rural residents can access the internet, and by providing them with technology-based training.

The Van Dijk (2006) research paper discussed the fact that a person first wants or desires to have a computer and to be connected to the Internet before having physical access to such equipment. With this, digital technology appears to be not only “have-nots,” but also “want-nots.” This explains the fact that even the primary sector desires and dreams (want-nots) of having mobile devices that they can use, such as smartphones. However, because of poverty, this desire remains a desire. Instead of buying (have-nots) a smartphone, they need to provide first food for their family.

The M-Mobile app is designed to provide the primary sector with alternative means of directly connecting and selling their products to consumers. In order to encourage them to have a secure income, this mobile app will allow them to explore mobile applications and learn new skills for mobile technology. Thus, the digital divide is reduced. Addressing the digital divide is essential for the country's economic growth, particularly the promotion of products made in the Philippines and its raw materials.

Research limitations/implications

The research initially focused on the intended outcomes of potential sample users. However, due to the limited mobility of people associated with community quarantine in the Philippines, imposed by the government to prevent the spread of coronavirus (COVID 19) pandemics, the researcher was able to gather a small sample of respondents, and therefore, she also adopted the Scoping Review Method as described by Arksey and O'Malley (2005) and analyzed the theories and outcomes of several published related literature.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. Conceptual framework of the study

The socio-economic conditions of the primary sector have become a field of interest, and the researcher has been inspired to undertake this research to provide them with an alternative way of selling their products and increasing their profits, as well as providing them with a stable and secure income. Many young people are passionate about using mobile apps and technology. This enthusiasm will also enable the primary sector to motivate their children to embrace their industry and encourage them to continue to advocate the sale of domestic products and goods. Hence, the goal of this research is to create a mobile application for the marketing and sale of domestic products between the primary sector and its customers.

The researcher used the following research instrument: (1) distributed a structured questionnaire using Likert Scale of 4 categories in order to collect information and data to address the problem statement, (2) review and evaluate related research, article and publications, and (3) the evaluation of different theories and results of studies using Triangular Analysis to assess the effectiveness of a mobile application in linking two or more people and its extent as a reliable source of income (Figure 1). The M-Mobile application has been designed and developed based on the outcome of the review of various related literature and the analysis of the theories presented (Figure 2).

The combination of two theoretical frameworks, such as the Expectancy-Value Theory and the Digital Divide Framework, has enabled the researcher to develop a conceptual framework for this study in relation to mobile applications for the primary sector. The findings were presented in the preliminary results of the methodology section, which were focused on demographics, such as personal information, the type of sector they belong, age and sex as well as their willingness to buy and use mobile phones, their experience, and socio-economic characteristics. The idea of mobile phone technology has been contextualized in such a way that the features useful to the intended recipient will be integrated into the software.

The primary sectors are not homogeneous and therefore have different types of data requirements as users of mobile apps. The aim of this research is to create a mobile application for two users: the seller (primary sector) and the purchaser (consumer) for the sale of domestic products. Expectancy Value Motivation Theory was used to assess how the user of the mobile device anticipates the usefulness and monetary advantages of these applications in the conduct of market operations, the distribution transfer, and the financial transaction. Eventually, challenges and opportunities were identified to further determine the ability of the primary sector to use mobile device infrastructure and to assess the potential for reducing or removing the technology gap or the so-called "digital divide" that is, in reality, the primary sector's actual situation. The findings of the present study focused on a limited sample population of 246 primary sector respondents and 225 consumer respondents, randomly chosen by the researcher using email address, facebook, messenger and other forms of communication. The results have been validated and confirmed by an analysis of other research findings and publications, particularly that the study requires data on mobile applications and domestic products in the Philippines. (Chisama, 2016).

Figure 3. The process flow of market activities using the mobile application

The study also concluded with the creation of M-Mobile application framework that can be used by the primary sector (Figure 3), particularly in the market and economic operation of domestic products and for their daily activities. This software has embraced a user-friendly app design that offers flexibility and typically handles users' uniform needs, regardless of the variety of products sold, and can often adapt to the unique capabilities and limitations of different mobile devices (Taylor and Levin, 2014). Customers/consumers expect that an application can provide distinct advantages, rather than simply function as virtual "repackaged" websites across mobile platforms (Newman et al. 2018).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This research was conducted to suggest an alternative way of supporting the primary sector through the development of a mobile application that meets their needs and improves their market activities.

The research sub-questions are stated, as follows:

1. What is the Respondents' assessment of their accessibility in terms of:
 - a) Internet
 - b) Delivery services
 - c) Payment centers
2. How can a mobile application affect the livelihood of the primary sector?
3. What effect does a mobile application have on the consumer/customer?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Ironically, most people in the primary sector have not completed their formal education, or some have not had the opportunity to experience the first level of formal education because of poverty. Their situation is not clear to the researcher's mind, because they are the ones who produce the basic element of all the products, and yet they belong to the poorest of the poor. The researcher's objective is to give this sector the opportunity to have a stable income while at the same time giving its family the hope of a better future, with the opportunity to learn and gain knowledge from technological innovation.

Mobile technology is a fast-growing field that is closely linked to an individual work and daily activities. Every day, new innovations with positive and negative effects contribute to the development of new methods of application that are expected to help the user (Jayatilleke, et al., 2018).

Moreover, due to ongoing developments in digital technology, including applications and networking tools, various networks have been developed to help rural residents communicate directly with people elsewhere. This will allow the public administration to lead the country by empowering rural people with mobile technology.

Mobile Device Application

The commonly used term "mobile device" refers to a range of devices that allow users from elsewhere to access information and messages (Karetso et al., 2014). Mobile devices are compact, lightweight gadgets such as smartphones, mobile phones or handsets, laptops, iPads, and so on (Jayatilleke, et al, 2018) that can be used conveniently anywhere at any time. Therefore, almost everyone has mobile devices, and for every activities, operation, and transaction they have, this device becomes an important gadget.

People install various applications in their smartphone and other devices to suit their needs and preferences. Mobile phones have influenced many research areas along with electronic networking systems (Traxler, 2009) and people's daily activities, including shopping, recreation, careers, and one-to-one social experiences. Innovation in mobile technology with a useful software application increases competition, enhances product performance, reduces risks and protects the environment while rising profitability, revenue,

economic growth and sustainability. Mobile phones have provided the primary sector with ways of connecting and selling their products in various online market venues. Mobile phones have allowed on-the-spot contact between the seller and the consumers to be connected. This will improve rural people's lives and thus give them the opportunity to take advantage of the technology and its continuing innovation.

The proliferation of mobile phones in developing countries has, over the past decade, contributed to the growth of this technology as an innovation tool (FAO 2012). Donovan (2011) suggested in his research that Mobile for Development (M4D) will concentrate on small-town life support services and the development of a software application. On the other hand, Fu and Akter (2011) noted that the use of mobile phones could improve the large proportion of rural residents at the bottom of the social ladder in many ways.

Since mobile phones are the first digital communications handset technology for many urban residents, primary sectors are concerned that the transition to some advanced digital technologies may have led rural communities to struggle more to see how and when mobile devices can be used productively (FAO, 2013). Mobile phones are clearly the most efficient tool for rural communications and key technologies to promote social change and strengthen local industries (Hernandez, 2012). This also provides tremendous opportunities for direct linkages to the primary sector through extension programs, professionals, suppliers and customer knowledge tools. Mobile phones offer a convenient tool for emergency, weather and business communication (Nyiri 2002, 2005). These information sharing technologies have provided a variety of avenues and practices for people to strengthen their business dealings and to focus on improving their sector and their field.

According to Aker (2011), SMS text messages are used because they are easy to create, customize and cost-effective for a wider selection of communication. Mobile phones can be a tool for on-site contact with buyers and customers (Chhachhar, 2012). However, irrespective of the extent to which it is used, there are also limitations on each mobile communication platform. These include a high level of illiteracy that requires real-time interaction with the primary sector and automated mobile phone voice systems (Duncombe 2012). However, nothing has been done by the public administration, a real-time interaction, known to the primary sector, to examine the types and functionalities of mobile devices that they need and the types of information that need to be disseminated to them and other rural areas.

The functionality and features of the mobile app should be independent or include the services required by the primary sector (Duncombe, 2012). Most rural people use conventional mobile phones with minimal alternative mobile interfaces (Chisama, 2016). It is therefore crucial to consider their situation and to provide the necessary reliable information for the development of mobile device applications. No matter how noble the aim of creating a mobile application for the primary sector is, if they only have a conventional mobile phone, this initiative will not help the primary sector to take a positive view of their current situation and to make use of technological innovation. The public administration should therefore interfere with the "digital divide" situation of the primary

sector.

A mobile application should provide users with access to vendor services and products that have evolved to fit their daily lives in a variety of ways (Wang et al., 2015). It is important that these relationships be improved by ensuring that their applications are convenient and easy to use as possible (i.e. ease of use would make it easier for consumers to integrate technology into their own concepts) (Newman et al., 2018). As a result, users will turn these increasingly intuitive devices into digital manifestations of their own personal desires, expectations and wishes – virtually anytime and anywhere, simply by clicking the mobile phone button to access the device (Belk, 2013).

In a study conducted by Shan Du and Hua Li (2019), m-commerce was described to be for convenience and ubiquity. They mentioned three groups that hold a key role in the growth of m-commerce. The first one is security and trust. Second, personalization and localization. And finally, the convenience of the consumer. Security and trust are the two main drivers of m-commerce economic growth (Chantzaras, 2017). Mobility is a crucial part of m-commerce. Given the current situation in the Philippines, where the government has announced a community quarantine, citizens are expected to stay at home. As a result, online shopping services are identified without constraint on time and place. As mobile networks grow, digital marketing is easy to manage and cost effective (Balasubramanian, et al., 2002). Many studies in the past have focused on the benefits of mobile commerce, and this provides a pillar for further studies, as shown in Figure 4.

Class of Application	Description	Examples
Mobile financial applications	Applications which is banking, brokerage and payment through mobile device	E-Bank, brokerage, mobile payment
Mobile advertising	Applications turning the network platform and mobile device into a selling tool	Mobile marketing
Mobile Inventory Management	Applications that concentrate on cutting down the number of inventory by mobile inventory management system	Location tracking of goods, boxes, troops and people
Proactive service management	Applications provide information and services to user immediately	Weather forecast, stock information
Wireless re-engineering	Applications attempting to enhance the quality of services using wireless mobile infrastructure	Instant payments by insurance companies
Mobile auction or reverse auction	Applications allowing users to search good and services in the form of auction	E-bay
Mobile entertainment services and games	Applications offering the entertainment to mobile users	Online video, music interactive games
Mobile Office	Applications attempting to provide the office environment to users anywhere	Video conferencing
Mobile distance education	Applications provide education to mobile users without the limitations of distance	Online class
Wireless data center	Applications that provide data storage services to mobile users for decision support	Cloud storage

Figure 4. Types of Mobile Commerce Applications

Source: Du and Li (2019)

Digital commerce is now shown in a number of mobile applications and website networks. It provides other functions and services, such as payment, advertising, online ordering, online transactions, and real-time headlines (Du and Li, 2019). Figure 4 illustrates

the classification of mobile applications for mobile commerce in terms of finance, technology, development tools and platforms. The increasing number of studies in emerging technologies support the idea that mobile applications are now the platform for economic and market activities due to convenience, easy to use, accessible anywhere and anytime without contact with the people around us.

Study (Frequency)	Research Question	Method	Findings
Wu, J.H (49)	What is the key driver behind the technology acceptance model in mobile commerce?	Empirical Analysis, and Mathematical Modeling	The paper indicated that perceived ease of use and perceived risk had a significant impact on behavioral intent.
Wei, T.T (46)	What drives the adoption of m-commerce in Malaysia?	Empirical Analysis	The findings revealed that perceived financial costs and trust have a significant impact on mobile users in Malaysia.
Ngai, E.W.T (46)	A literature review for mobile commerce applications	Literature Review	This paper reviewed the literature on applications for m-commerce and provided future directions for research
Venkatesh, V. (45)	What do you do to make mobile commerce more usable?	Empirical Analysis	Customer interface experience can create good customer sensory satisfaction.
Chong, A.Y.L (45)	Predicting consumer decisions on mobile commerce in China	Empirical Analysis	The paper extended the TAM and DOI models and described the newly added variables, such as trust and multi-service. There are some control variables, such as the level of education and gender.
Kim, H.W (38)	Value-based Adoption of Mobile Internet	Empirical Analysis	The paper provided the value perspective for researcher to understand Mobile Internet and Communication Technology
Li, Y.M (35)	How aesthetics design affects consumer trust.	Empirical Analysis	Good aesthetics of mobile website design can increase trust in m-commerce
Zhang, L.Y (32)	How cultural factors affect the adoption of mobile commerce	Empirical Analysis, and Mathematical Modeling	The paper stated that culture has a very significant impact on mobile commerce by using structural equation modeling
Kim, C. (31)	What are the factors that affect the intention to use mobile payment?	Empirical Analysis	The paper analyzed the characteristics of the m-payment system and its applicability to different types of mobile payment users.
Barnes, S.J (30)	What is the value chain of mobile commerce made of?	Literature Review	It analyzed key players and technologies in the value chain of m-commerce and provided a basic study strategy.

Figure 5. Top 10 most cited references

Source: Du and Li (2019)

In Figure 5, the authors Du and Li (2019) provided a list of the top 10 most cited mobile commerce sources. Six of the ten studies used only empirical analysis as their methodological tool, and only two used literature reviews, while two other authors used mixed empirical analysis and mathematical modeling. Most of these writers used an empirical research tool to study mobile commerce. The perceived financial cost, perceived risk, a wide range of services and culture of these publications have a positive influence on the attitude and behavioral cause; the controlling factors, such as academic level and gender, may also have an impact on the final outcome of their study (Du and Li, 2019).

Figure 6. Top Shopping Apps in the Philippines (Google Play Store)

Source: Mobile Action

Figure 6 shows that internet transactions of mobile apps in the Philippines are not based solely on Philippine goods, the majority of which are already produced and supplied by secondary sectors. Shopee, Singapore's e-commerce platform offering a variety of items of any kind and of any use, is one of the top 10 shopping apps in the Philippines. Next is Lazada, an online retail business run by the Alibaba Group and offering all kinds of items, much the same as Shopee. All of these top ten mobile shopping services are run by foreigners and none of them offers a platform to market either only domestic raw materials or products made in the Philippines.

Company Name	Category	Products	Description
E-palengke	On-line shopping (website only)	Fruits, vegetables, seafood, meats, eggs, herbs, rice grains, and charcoal	Product sources originated from different suppliers, traders and farmers in different regions of the Philippines.
Ecocsi Food Inc	On-line shopping (website only)	Seafood, chicken, pork beef, process foods, fries and halal products	Product sources originated from different suppliers, and traders. They also sell frozen and process products
Mayani	On-line shopping (website only)	Vegetables, Frozen Meat and Fish, and other local packed products	Product sources originated from different suppliers, and traders. They also sell frozen products and secondary products
Fresh Produce PH	On-line shopping (website only)	Fruits, vegetables, chicken, eggs, rice grains and sugar	Product sources originated from different suppliers, traders and farmers
The Green Grocer	On-line shopping (website and mobile app)	Grocery products, meat, vegetables, fruits, beverages, chicken, frozen foods, packed products, snacks and dessert	Product sources originated from different suppliers, traders and farmers in Tagavtay, Laguna, Batangas, Banquet, Negros and Bukidnon.
Zagane	On-line shopping (website only)	Fruits, vegetables, frozen meat and seafood, rice and eggs	It is an online platform for fresh vegetables and fruits direct from the local farmers in the Philippines.
Bukid Fresh	On-line shopping (website only)	Coffee, herbs and spices, grains, eggs, vegetables, fruits, salt and sugar	Product sources originated from different suppliers, traders and farmers
Future Fresh	On-line shopping (website only)	Leafy vegetables	They have a farm of their own. They also supply their products to supermarkets.
Session Groceries	On-line shopping (IOS/Android application only)	Seafood, secondary products and vegetables	Products sources supplied by different partners company and producers. They also source their products directly from farmers

Figure 7. Online sale of local products in the Philippines

The researcher found nine common online sales of Philippine products and raw materials, as shown in Figure 7, but only Green Grocer Manila has mobile apps and websites, while Session Groceries has mobile application only. However, the researcher noted that online shopping in the Philippines is not focused on products produced by the primary industry, but rather on the sale of supermarket goods, processed food and frozen food, and many of the products have been supplied by a number of suppliers and traders. Only a few online websites sell farm products directly to consumers, but not products of other primary sectors, such as fishermen, miners and forestry. Many of these online sales have only a website portal, but there are no mobile applications available. Sales of domestic goods on these platforms are limited to a specific category of products only, and not all products produced by the primary sector are advertised for sale.

As a result, the mobile market for domestic products has been described as extremely challenging, particularly in primary sectors which do not have a mobile phone that is compatible with the installation of a software application or which do not have access to the Internet to use the application. The Public Administration, in particular the Department of Agriculture (DA), is mandated to promote agricultural development by providing the policy framework, public investment and support services needed for domestic and export-oriented business enterprises. The Department's primary concern is to improve farm income and create work opportunities for farmers, fishermen and others. This promotes public participation and involvement in sustainable agriculture, crafts and fisheries through sectoral representation in policy-making bodies, ensuring that departmental strategies, initiatives and services are planned and implemented to meet their needs (DA RFO). This research on mobile technology applications, such as the M-Mobile App, can also help to make this a reality, with the aim of promoting and enabling farming and fishing communities and the private sector to provide adequate, sustainable and accessible food for every Filipino and stable income for all.

Mobile applications in support of Philippine domestic goods as a means of promoting brand identity have been developed in this research. It is a platform for networking, e-commerce, collaboration, public sector partnerships and advertising opportunities to improve Philippine products produced by the primary sector, to help attract new consumers and to enhance the loyalty of current customers/consumers (Wang et al., 2016) as well as to market and promote the various products of the regions where they belong. This economic activity will strengthen the Philippine domestic product and support the growth of the country's economy and help the primary sector improve its technical capabilities through capacity building, as well as to foster meaningful public participation, increase civic engagement and encourage private sector participation through partnership and collaboration.

There are several barriers to the progress and extent of this transformation, but the added benefit of direct links between rural and urban people or elsewhere cannot be ignored. The distribution of information in many disciplines that drive rural development, including agriculture, health, education and banking, has dramatically changed the use of mobile

devices (Chachhar & Hassan, 2013). It is therefore important to understand how mobile technology should be used by the primary sector to access market information services in the Philippines. For example, fishermen have shown that mobile phones have facilitated and expanded their markets by finding new customers and offering competitive prices both internally and externally on their local shorelines. The mobile phone helped fishermen to determine how and when they would market their catch (Salia, et al., 2011). This type of digital technology often reduces the gap and possible harm to these fishermen before going to the sea, by utilizing the mobile application that offers weather updates, they can monitor weather conditions. Using this tool, the fishermen may also contact the market wholesaler to determine whether to offer their goods at a good rate or to wait for an appropriate time at a reasonable price (Chachhar, 2012).

Most farmers and fishermen in the villages were living in remote areas. They remain illiterate due to lack of awareness and sound information about prices, weather, rules and regulations, news, training, credit markets and market opportunities. The researcher believes that, following the complete development of the M-Mobile Application, including all the information needed by the primary sector, this application will provide a good opportunity for farmers, miners, foresters, animal breeders and fishermen to communicate, advertise and exchange information and weather updates that may improve their lives (Cecchini & Scott, 2003). Mobile phones have increased data and understanding of business opportunities and the ability to operate more efficiently (Myhr & Ståhl 2006). In addition, consideration should also be given to how farmers and fishermen have used modern technologies to improve their living conditions (Dey, 2009).

However, there are barriers to agricultural information experienced by the primary sector, such as lack of access to newspapers, television, radio and landlines (Aker, 2011). According to Cole and Fernando (2012), due to a lack of resources, the Government's rural expansion program was unable to gather data beyond the easy-to-access program and to obtain immediate benefits from the raw materials offered by farmers. In many studies, lack of awareness among local citizens has had a significant impact on the development of production and business, leading to irrational decision-making (Molony, 2006). This simply means that the information symmetry has been constantly challenged as most primary sectors have not been able to access economic information services in a timely, accurate, consistent and reliable manner (Aker, 2011; Duncombe, 2012; Baumüller, 2012).

In the Duncombe (2012) study, it was noted that prior to the implementation of a mobile application such as M-mobile application, it is first necessary to understand the needs and circumstances of the primary sectors. This includes the use of context-specific studies on access to mobile information services in agriculture, fisheries and forestry, mining, livestock and craft industries. The level of the "digital divide" or the extent of the gap between the primary sector and technology should also be determined.

However, past research in most developing countries has overlooked the challenges of 'digital divide' in terms of basic personal skills (e.g. literacy or digital skills), motivational qualities and the use of information from mobile phones. Generally speaking, the

knowledge needs of the primary sectors are divided into three categories: production system management, financial inclusion and market access (Vodafone, 2005). Although the increasing popularity of online mobile communication information systems is relatively new in most rural communities, there is still a low level of awareness of current developments and a lack of digital skills in the local communities.

There are challenges that the public administration needs to address when implementing mobile application technology. In their study entitled "The Knowledge Mapping of Mobile Commerce Research: A Visual Analysis Based on I-Model," Du and Li (2019) illustrate the integrated framework of mobile commerce research as follows (Figure 8):

Figure 8. The Integrated Framework of Mobile Commerce researches

This framework shows that the behavior and attitude of a person is greatly influenced by people, technology, information and social aspects. These aspects show how a person has perceived a certain situation, and that can influence their decision. For example, if the primary sector as a mobile user does not have an access to the Internet, despite having a mobile phone that is compatible with a mobile application, regardless of their desire to use it, they will not use it because they do not have access to the Internet. As a result, their approach to technology is influenced by the fact that they do not use it because of the lack of internet access available to them, given the supposed positive effect of this mobile application in their lives.

Primary Sector

The primary sector has been chosen as the main subject of this study because they are lacking in many ways and was considered as among the poorest of the poor with no or have limited access to technology and less representation to government decision-making and policy making.

As of June 3, 2020, the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) preliminarily estimated the incidence of poverty in 2018, for example, 10 of the 14 basic sectors listed in Republic Act 8425, or the Social Reform and Poverty Alleviation Act and those who are rural residents has been shown in Figure 3. The incidence of poverty among persons with disabilities (aged 15 and over) has also been produced and released, to wit:

Source: Merged data file of the 2015 Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES) and January 2016 Labor Force Survey (LFS) and preliminary merged data file of the 2018 FIES and January 2019 LFS, Philippine Statistics Authority

Note: r – revised; the 2015 estimates were revised/updated based on the following: a) rebasing of the Consumer Price Index (CPI) market basket of prices from 2006 to 2012; b) adoption of the 2015 Census of Population (PopCen) results for the weights in the merged FIES-LFS; and c) updated urban-rural classification of barangays based on the 2015 PopCen.

Figure 9. Poverty Incidence among the Basic Sectors (%):2015 and 2018

Figure 9 illustrate the highest rates of poverty in key sectors in 2018 were 31.6, 26.2, 24.5 and 23.9 for farmers, fishermen, people living in rural areas and children belonging to families below official poverty levels. Both these industries accounted for 40.8, 36.9, 34.0 and 33.5 per cent in 2015, with the highest rates of poverty recorded (Mapa, 2020).

Rapidly increasing demand for performance and productivity in the sector is important for ensuring the affordability of food and purchasing power, particularly among people living below the poverty line. Agriculture, mining, forestry, livestock and fisheries sectors provide food and vital raw materials for the people of the Philippines. The sector's development is therefore crucial to the sustainability of inclusive economic growth and poverty reduction. Increased dependence on industry production has also put a great deal of pressure on its natural ecosystems.

Although the share of agriculture to domestic revenue decreases proportionately, despite the rise of total economic progress in recent years, both the value of agricultural exports and of the industry appear to expand. According to the PSA, agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fisheries together accounted for 9.7% of the Philippines' GDP in the fourth quarter in 2016, down 1.1% annually. In recent years, extreme weather imbalances have resulted in unpredictable production. For instance, in 2015, with the major damage caused by Typhoon Lando, long dry spells have adversely affected the industry, which has recorded a production increase of just 0.11% since 2014. Production in crops and fisheries has dropped respectively by 1.95 and by 1.96% during 2015, while poultry and livestock segments increased by 5.7% and 3.8%, respectively. This climate change and the extended dry spell had a detrimental impact on crops in 2016, which contributed to a decrease of 1.3% in agriculture. As in 2015, increases in productivity in the livestock and poultry sectors were insufficient to compensate for losses in agricultural production and fisheries (Oxford Business Group).

Unsustainable activities in the production of agriculture have resulted in the loss of biodiversity and severe problems with the water supply. Climate change has intensified established flaws in the industry. Therefore, economic reforms will concentrate on changing the sector to be not just highly competitive but also climate-responsive, environmentally friendly and sustainable (NEDA, 2013).

Market Mobile Application

M-Mobile technology can provide the easiest and most accessible means for local communities, particularly the primary sector, to access government services and convenient sales transactions by moving from traditional paper-based services to wired internet-based services to wireless internet services (Karetsos et al., 2014) and then to mobile software/application.

Mobile applications or apps are also classified as Self-Service Technology (SST) devices that enable users to participate in different components of provider-customer experiences, such as knowledge quest, cost scanners and actual transactions (Kaushik and Rahman, 2015). Consumers invest about 25% of their real device time on shopping applications, to concentrate more time on simple and quick texting, sports, videos, shows, and news/ information applications (comScore, 2014). Such trends give vendors the ability to use mobile device strategies to take back or improve the business climate in the face of the inevitable existence of major online vendors (such as Lazada, Shopee) (Gupta, 2013). Nonetheless, they often face crucial obstacles because of consumer and reference management (e.g. mobile versus in-store)

The innovation of a mobile device application providing a channel for sale and purchase directly to the primary sector, which also offers competitive opportunities, should be considered, and the commitment of local government is important, and its political role for good governance and public service innovation can be presented in apolitical ways (Paschoal and Wegrich, 2019). Connections between the primary sector and consumers in urban cities and other neighboring provinces, local government should take an active part

in providing them with a convenient, quick and easy way to carry out economic activities and transactions, a commitment that can be derived from creating policy-based mobile commerce intended for the sale of domestic goods and products.

This economic activity involves six players: the **primary sector** which supplies and extracts basic food and meets the needs of the consumers; the **delivery services or the private transport organization** which will be the primary sector's partner for the shipment of purchase products and goods; **local government unit** who will support and assist the primary sector in capacity-building, addressing its operational needs and promoting domestic products; the **national government**, particularly the Department of Agriculture, will devise an approach addressing innovation for trade-based policies, plans and design projects and programs, providing a stable source of income for the primary sector while enhancing their technological capacity, making it easier for them to operate and promote their domestic products and opening an opportunity for export-oriented business; the **consumer**, who buy goods and products should be encouraged to patronize or buy products or goods produced by the primary sector or products made in the Philippines; and finally, a **mobile application administrator** who designed and maintained the applications efficiency. This mobile device application will provide an opportunity for partnerships and collaboration that brings together different stakeholders to develop, implement more holistic and integrated strategies to promote Philippine-made products.

Domestic products of the Philippines

The Philippines's major agricultural crops are rice, corn, coconut, sugarcane, banana, cassava, pineapple, and vegetables. Dog, horse, carabao, goat, and dairy products are the major livestock products while chicken and duck are the top products for poultry. The Philippines has huge areas of coastlines and possesses an array of fish species. Tuna and tuna-like varieties, sardines, anchovy, round-scads, and slip-mouth are some of the main species (Philippine Consulate General, Canada).

The distribution of the gross domestic product (GDP) is generally divided between the agricultural, industrial and service sectors. Agriculture contributed to 9.3% of GDP in 2018, making it the lowest recorded contribution to GDP in the country's history. In the 1980s, agriculture constituted one-quarter of the country's GDP, with almost one-third in the 1970s. In the meantime, 30.8% and 60% respectively were in the industrial and service sectors. It should also be noted that over time, the share of industrial production has decreased, and the sector of services has increased significantly (Bajpai, 2020).

In the Article written by Bajpai, 2020, the author stated that the Philippines has shifted significantly from an agricultural to an industrial and service-oriented economy. In 1980, agriculture contributed for around one-fourth of the country's GDP, however over the years it has decreased to 9.3%. The Philippines has slowly transitioned from agricultural to industrial and service-oriented economies. Agriculture contributed to about one-fourth of the nation's GDP in 1980, but this has decreased to 9.3% over the years. The agricultural sector includes hunting, forestry, fishing, planting and harvesting, livestock production and crop cultivation. The sector accounted for approximately about 25% of the working

population. The major agricultural products are rice, sugar cane, corn, coconuts, pineapples, bananas, cassava (manioc), mangoes, tapioca, fish, pork, beef, and eggs. Figure 10 shows the domestic products (primary and secondary) of the Philippines by region and province.

Region	Provinces	Primary Product	Secondary Products
REGION I	Ilocos Norte	Garlic, Rice, Corn, Legume, Root crops, Tobacco, Sinmegwelas, Swine and Cattle	Ceramics, Iron works, Loom weaving, Furniture and Chicharon
	Ilocos Sur	Sugarcane, Ginger, Bamboo, Ube, Coffee beans, Rice, Rambutan, Calamansi, and Garlic	Sugarcane vinegar, Calamansi, Sugarcane wine, Bagnet, Nata de coco, Oriedmango and Longganisa
	La Union	Mushroom, Bangus, Sea urchin, Grapes, Bamboo, Perhay, Daing, Corn and Honey	Softbroom, Handloom weaving, Basi, Pottery, and Baskets
	Pangasinan	Malagkit, Dangit, Nipa, Mango and Bangus	Puto, Sawali making, Tapa, Dried salted fish and Longganisa
REGION II	Batanes	Coconut, Garlic, Turmeric, Fish, Rice, Corn, Onion, Ube and Gabi	Nipa hat, Basket, Softbrooms, Native bag, Souvenirs, Furnitures, Basket, Bags, and Clothings
	Cagayan	Rice, Corn, Peanuts, Beans, and Fruits	Bamboo products, Rattan made products and Hardwood made products
	Isabela	Corn, Rice, and Mung beans	Pancit cabagan, Binallay, Moriccos, Dinengdeng, Inatata, Allingbelen Longganisa, Bibinglang kamim and Lechon cordero
	Nueva Vizcaya	Rice, Corn, Fruits, Vegetables, Pomelo, Ponkan, and Oranges	Rice cakes, Lumpia, Pancit, and Dinuguan
	Quirino	Banana, Rice, Corn and Woods	Basket, Bags, Beads, Bamboo jars, Fossilized flowers, Woodcrafts, Banana chips, Fruit wine, and Ginger tea
REGION III	Aurora	Rice, Coconuts, Coffee, Bananas, Rootcrops, Corn, Citrus Fruits, Peanuts, and Abaca	Native fan, Baskets, Bags, Furniture, Hats, Slippers, Banig, Lambanog and Tuba
	Bataan	Banana, Mango, and Palay	Tinapa, Brooms, Ropes, and Shell crafts
	Bulacan	Fruits, Vegetable, Root crops, Ornamentals, and industrial crops	Tuba ng sasa, Sukang Bulacan and Honey bee products
	Pampanga	Rice, Corn, Sugarcane, and Tilapia	Murcon, Betute Tagak, Pindang Kalobaw, Adobong Kamaru, Sisig, Buro, Bringhe, Alligus, Bulanglang Kapampangan, Tibuk-tibuk, Halo-halo, Panecillos de san nicolas, and Turrones de caouy
	Nueva Ecija	Rice, Corn, Onion, Garlic, Melon, and Mango	Icecream, Sherbet, Pinapitan, Batotay, Bangus Spaghetti, Buko Lumpia, and Carabao's milk dairy products
	Tarlac	Rice, Sugarcane, Corn, Coconut, Eggplant, Garlic, Onion, Mango, Banana, Calamansi, and Fish	Binalay grilled suman, Dried kamias, Mango vinegar, Water lily bag, and Leche flan in an egg
	Zambales	Rice, Corn, Vegetables, Mango, Root crops, Gold, Fish, and Stones	Bagnet, Dried mangoes, Gimipang, Pastillas, and Botolan
REGION IV-A	Cavite	Rice, Corn, Coffee beans, Coconuts, Cut flowers, and Vegetables	Tablea, Coffee, Acharcutery, Mushroom, Dairy products, Rice cakes, Vinegar, Bamboo products, Burnay jars, and Smoked fish
	Laguna	Rice, Coffee beans, Corn, Vegetables, Sugar canes, Garden products, Bangus, Tilapia, and Bighead carp	Buko pie, Teasty puto, Espasol, Uraio, Salted Eggs, Kinulob na itik, Mesong puti and Bulalo
	Batangas	Coffee beans, Fish, and Coconut	Kapeng baretto, Tapang taal, Lambanog, Bagoong balayan, Tamarind wine, Barong tagalog, Wedding dress, Embroideries, Panutsa, and Alcarang calaca
	Rizal	Cucumber, Cabbage, Lettuce, Ampalaya, Beans, Okra, Mango, Cashew, Citrus Rambutan, Avocado, Santol, Atis, and Jackfruit	Pottery, Pork belly, Rocks and Botong, Pizza, Vocalan and fairies, and Fried pork
	Quezon	Coconut, Fish and Rice	Lambanog, Yema cake, Longganisang Lucban, Pansit Lucban, and Oregano juice

Region	Provinces	Primary Product	Secondary Products
REGION IV-B	Mindoro	Sugarcane, Peanuts, Calfish, Milkfish, Tilapia, Livestock, Onion, and Salt	Mangyan Handicrafts, Wood crafts, Banana chips, Processed meat, Bahag, Slippers, and Calamansi products
	Marinduque	Coconuts, Dills, Cassava, Cane, and Bamboo	Bibingka and Vinegar
	Romblon	Coconut, Abaca, Fish, and Crabs	Sarsa, Balichow ng Gamus, Ginataang Langka, Peanut Butter, Combi- Ginger and Turmeric, and Fresh seafood
	Palawan	Cashew, Honey, Buti, Daing, Tuna, and banana	Wild pig figurine, Banana chips, Turmeric and Ginger tea, Coconut jam, Blday, Rain stick, Pearls and Jewelleries
REGION V	Albay	Coconut, Sili, Rice, Sugar, Pili, and Abaca	Hats, Bicol express, Pinangat, Pili nuts, Tinilmok, Kinunot, Longanisa, Bags, Mats, Slippers, and Abaca products
	Camarines Norte	Grain crops, Vegetables, Coconuts, Root crops, Fruits, Gold, Iron Ore, and Pineapple	Copra, Jewelry Crafts, Coconut related Products, Sinantol, Kinunot, Tinumok, Bicol express, and Pili roll
	Camarines Sur	Pili, Coconut, Rice, Corn, Vegetables, and Fish	Coconut related Products, Sinantol, Kinunot, Tinumok, Bicol express, and Pili roll
	Catanduanes	Crab, Pili, and Cacao	Mud crabs, Fresh seafood, Cacao, Bicol kakanin, and Sea breeze
	Masbate	Corn, Rice, Root crops, Coconuts, Gold, Iron, and Copper	Furnitures, Copra, Handicrafts, and Jewelleries
	Sorsogon	Rice, Coconut, Abaca, Pili nut, Root crops, and Vegetables	Kingang, Baluko, Suman lehia, Timitim, and Pili conserva
	Abra	Rice, Corn, Vegetables, Coffee, Tobacco, and Coconut	Woven materials, Muscovado sugar, Bamboo products, and Wood crafts
REGION-CAR	Benguet	Gold, Copper, Iron, Honey, Bees wax, Salt, Livestock, Potatoes, Baguio beans Peas, Strawberry, Cabbage, Broccoli, Cauliflower, Lettuce, Sayote, and Carrots	Beads, Blanket, Plates, Jars, and Strawberry jam
	Iligao	Rice and Coffee	Inilagim and binaod
	Kalinga	Rice, Corn, Coffee, Banana, Orange, and Rattan fruit	Coffee greens, Rice wine, Garments, Bags, Decorations, and Clothes
	Apayao	Palay, Corn, Coffee, Rootcrops, Vegetables, Lansones, Citrus, Bananas, Pineapple, Durian, Santol, Rambutan, Coconut, and Mangosteen	Coffee greens, Rice wine, Garments, Bags, Decorations, and Clothes
	Mountain Province	Bamboo, Rattan, Rice, and Coffee	Bags, Purses, Pouches, Wallets, Blazers, Skirts, and Wall decorations
	Aklan	Loom, Coconut, Prawns, Crabs and Bangus	Raffia cloth, Copra, Processed food Products, Furniture, Metal craft, Bricks, Weaved hats, Mats, and Gifts
	Antique	Rice, Fish, Livestock, Poultry, Sugarcane, Fruits, Vegetables, and Seaweeds	Muscovado sugar and Copra
REGION VI	Capiz	Rice, Corn, Coconut, Sugarcane, Banana, Cut flower, Prawn, bangus, Bluemarin, Squid, Oysters, Shrimp, Seaweed, and Angel wings	Dried fish, Lobster, Diwal, Crab, Barquillos, Pinasugbo, Suman, and Turon
	Guimaras	Mangoes, Palay, Coconuts, Livestock, Poultry, Fish, Gold, Iron, and Copper	Handicrafts, Jewelleries, Mango pizza, Mango beer, Mango jam, and Mango bibingka
	Iloilo	Rice, Fruits, and Vegetables	Processed foods, Gifts, and Furniture
	Negros Occidental	Silk, Fish, Dianggit, Bangus, Peanuts, Squid, and Bamboo	Dried fish, Giftware and Holiday decor, Bamboocraft, Squid rings, dairy products, Turones de mani, and Processed bangus
	Bohol	Rice, Corn, Coconut, Mango, and Poultry	Peanut kisses, Dairy box, Tableya, Shirts, and Magnets
REGION VII	Cebu	Corn, Rice, Mango, Coconut, Banana, Peanut, Tuna, Lapu lapu, Sardines, Flying fish, Crab, and Prawn	Dried mangoes, Otap, Rosquillos, Masareal, Local shirts, and Lapu-lapu guitars
	Negros Oriental	Rice, Corn, Vegetables, Fruit, Abaca, and Tobacco	Stone craft, Cloth weaving, Basket knitting, Food processing, and T shirt printing
	Siquijor	Corn, Coconut, Cassava, Rice, Rubber, Mango, and Jackfruit	Copra, Knitting craft, Toy, and Garment
REGION VIII	Leyte	Abaca fibre, Banana, Rice, Corn, Poultry meat, Fruits, Vegetable, Tuna, Flying fish, Mackerel, Shells, Lobsters, Ceramic, Coconut, and Bamboo	Moron, Binagol, Suman-latik, Roscas, Bukayo, and Vacuum fried jackfruit
	Biliran	Palay, Coconut, Banana, Mango, and Citrus fruits	Dried fish, Citronella oil, Lumber, Coconut oil, Copra, Sulfur, white clay ceramics, Placemats, Baskets, Fashion bags, Trays, and Shell crafts
	Southern Leyte	Abaca fibre, Banana, Rice, Corn, Fruits, Vegetables, Poultry meat, Tuna, Flying fish, mackerel, Shells, and Lobsters	Ceramics, Copra, and Bamboo made products
	Western Leyte	Rice, Coconut, Abaca, Root crops, Vegetables, Seaweed, Mollusk, Oyster, Crabs shells, and Fish	Clothing, Jewelleries, and Accessories
	Eastern Samar	Pineapple, Corn, Vegetables, Coconut, Banana, Mackerel, Tuna tropical aquarium fishes, Lobster, Crab, Shells, and Seaweeds	Coconut wine, Mussels, Crackers, Turmeric tea, Chocolate moron, Salokara, Sashimi, Calamansi concentrate, Calamansi juice, Jelly calamansi extract, Pineapple jelly, Pineapple vinegar, Sweet potato, and Cassava chips
	Northern Samar	Banana, Peanut, and Oil	Abaca made products

Region	Provinces	Primary Product	Secondary Products
REGION IX	Zamboanga del Norte	Coconut, Corn, Palay, Banana, Cassava, Rubber, Vegetables, Chromite, Gold Manganese, Asbestos, and Silica	Dry cassava, Peanut biscuit, and Durian chips
	Zamboanga del Sur	Rice, Corn, and Banana	Coconut oil
	Zamboanga Sibugay	Rice, Corn, Coconuts, Rubber, Fruit trees, Vegetables, Tobacco, Coffee, and Cacao	Alavar saure, Yakan weaves, Yakan footwear, Malaysian goods, and Lechon
REGION X	Bukidnon	Rice, Corn, Coffee, Rubber, Pineapple, Tomato, Sugarcane, Flowers, and Cassava	Sugar and Vinegar
	Carmiguin Islands	Coconut, Cassava, Banana, Kamote, Palay, Corn, Fruits, Coffee, and Vegetables	Bags and Pastillas
	Lenao del Norte	Rice, Fruits, Corn, and Copra	Jars, Dried fish, and Buko pie
	Misamis Occidental	Coconut, Banana, and Palay	Coconut oil, Cooking oil, Lard, Margarine, Laundry soap, Ceramic gifts Toys, Housewares, and Banana chips
	Misamis Oriental	Pineapple and Coconut	Canned pineapple, Crudo coco oil, Finished lumber, Wood products Fatty alcohol, Coco shell, and Charcoal
REGION XI	Compostella Valley	Rice, Coconut, Cacao, Coffee, Papaya, Mango, Pineapple, Durian, and Banana	Pineapple juice, Coconut oil, and Durian candy
	Davao del Norte	Mango, Pomelo, Banana, Coconut, Pineapple, Papaya, Mangosteen, Durian, and Cacao	Durian candy, Biscone, Mangosteen cube, Durian cube, and Pomelo lemon pie
	Davao del Sur	Coconut, Rice, Corn, Banana, Durian, Mango, and Pineapple	Durian candy
	Davao Occidental	Fish, Banana, and Coconut	Durian candy, Biscone, Mangosteen cube, Durian cube, and Pomelo lemon pie
	Davao Oriental	Coconut, Rice corn, Banana, Durian, Mango, and Pineapple	Pineapple juice, Coconut oil, and Durian candy
REGION XII	South Cotabato	Pineapple, Papaya, Asparagus, Fruits, Vegetables, Corn, Coffee, and Banana	Tribal products
	Cotabato	Pineapple, Papaya, Asparagus, Fruits, Vegetables, Corn, Coffee, Banana and Cut-flowers	Tribal products
	Sultan Kudarat	Rice, Corn, Coconuts, Coffee, Banana, Mangoes, Durians, African palm, Poultry, Root crops, and Potatoes	Handicrafts, Palm oil, and Cottage
	Sarangani	Coconut, Corn, Rice, Banana, Mango, Durian, Rubber, Sugarcane, Pineapple, Asparagus, and Coffee	Marinated milkfish bangus, Handicrafts, Palm oil, and Cottage
REGION XIII	Agusan del Norte	Rice, Coconut, Corn, Mango, Banana, Palm oil, Vegetables and Prawn	Nilusak, Nilambiran, and Balanghoy
	Agusan del Sur	Gold, Mudfish, Catfish, and Tilapia	Local liquors and Baskets
	Surigao del Norte	Rice, Corn, Vegetables, Root crops, Coconut, Copra, Banana, and Tuna	Salted fish, Bayong, Puto, Vinegar, Dried fish, and Malunggay extract
	Surigao del Sur	Rice, Corn, Vegetables, Root crops, Coconut, Copra, Banana, and Tuna	Rice cakes, Poot-poot, Gimamos, Kinilaw, Dry pianga, and Gigaquit rhum
REGION-BARMM	Dinagat Islands	Seafood, Coconut, Lumber, and Mines	Tea, Cinnamon tea, Saang sauteed, Rice cakes, and Carabeef kinilaw
	Basilan	Jackfruit, Rice, Bamboo, and Banana	Sageel kinilaw, Puto, Sinilanglag, Ginataang langka, Kaliya, and Yakan chicken
	Lanao del Sur	Crab, Rice, and Coconut	Palapa, Rice cake, Suman, and Cooked crab
	Maguindanao	Wet rice, Squash, Potatoes, Tomatoes, Beans, Coconut milk, Bananas, Mangoes Guavas, Cassavas, Durian, Salt water fish, Shell fish, and Water buffalo	Tipas, Durian candy, and Bang
	Sulu	Coconut, Cassava, Abaca fiber, Coffee beans, Lansones, Jackfruit, Durian Mangosteen, Marang, and Seaweed	Beef kulima, Chicken piyanggang, and Piyssak
	Tawi-tawi	Seaweeds, Copra, Rootcrops, Fruits, and Vegetables	Seaweeds products, Baskets, Batang buruk, Bags, and Furnitures

Figure 10. List of Philippine Domestic Products per Region and Provinces

Figure 10 shows the list of local products of the Philippines by region and province. This figure represents how rich the Philippines is in natural resources and demonstrates that each province has its own unique products, as well as products similar to other provinces, such as rice, corn or maize, bananas and coconut. Almost every region produces grain of rice, corn, and coconut. That alone, when properly sold directly from the primary sector to consumers (Ps2C), will make their lives sufficient for them to live above the poverty line.

Slow economic activity and poor performance in the Philippine agricultural sector have resulted in an increase or high incidence of poverty in the sector (Figure 9). The lack of knowledge of government initiatives, schemes, programs and policies in the primary

sector affects their effectiveness and their level of confidence in the government. The primary sector expects the government to help them protect their work especially during climate change, particularly in times of typhoon and drought, but due to lack of information and distance, this climate change has significantly affected them. This is one of the factors that the research has tried to address.

Fortunately, the situation now seems to improve because the government spends heavily in this sector. The government funds the Department of Agriculture's (DA) initiatives and programs in an attempt to improve food security, rural jobs, and infrastructure. The government should aim to take steps on post-harvest financial loss while reducing the prices of goods and stabilizing labor costs included in the Farm Mechanization, National Organic Agriculture, and Post-Harvest Development (Bajpai, 2020).

Government-wide policies, initiatives and the emergence of the latest digital mobile application will pave the way for the competitiveness and production of the primary sector to be strengthened in the near future.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a mixed research methodology using a structured survey questionnaire in Likert Scale in four categories, and Scoping Review Method. The Scoping Review Method was used to identify, prioritize, and identify gaps and/or priorities of the primary sector. Using Triangulation analysis, the results will be interpreted and synthesized by analyzing the outcome of the present survey and evaluating the findings of researchers on mobile application and mobile commerce.

The researcher analyzed how mobile technology can be used to provide assistance for primary industries to promote their local goods, increase their sales and influence consumers to purchase and endorse local produces or products made in the Philippines. This research focuses on developing the mobile phone application as a platform for domestic market operations and transactions.

The instrument used in this study is a structured questionnaire to collect data from primary sector respondents and consumers. The researcher focuses on the majority of topics in literature-based instruments and almost identical academic studies. The questions included a variety of subjects, such as: 1) demographic information and private information; 2) questions related to the situation of the respondents. There are 246 primary sector respondents in different provinces and 225 respondents at different locations in the Philippines.

To strengthen the research outcomes, Triangulation Analysis (Figure 11) will be used to interpret multiple data sources and materials, several theories and publications, and multiple approaches and perspectives. Triangulation Analysis is "the use of several approaches to a study to increase trust in the ensuing results" (Bryman, n.d., p.1)

Figure 11. Triangulation Analysis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data were collected online through Google forms in the month of June 2020. Respondents were provided with a link to the questionnaire mostly through their email address and the FB Messenger. The survey was participated by 246 primary sector respondents and 225 consumer respondents from the different regions and provinces of the Philippines. However, the survey is not, in any manner, a comprehensive representation of people's perceptions in rural areas as well as in primary sectors, as there is no equal representation by province or region due to the restrictions on community quarantine imposed by the government. The researcher, therefore, also used the Scoping Review Method to support the researcher's findings

Demographic data of respondents are summarized as follows:

1. Sex

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Sex

A. Primary Sector		
Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	141	57.3
Female	105	42.7
Prefer not to say	0	0
Total	246	100
B. Consumer		
Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	121	53.8
Female	98	43.55
Prefer not to say	6	2.65
Total	225	100

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage of respondents by sex. The data on sex has been collected to know who is usually using a mobile phone when it comes to selling and buying. 42.7% or 105 of the respondent primary sectors are female, while 57.3% or 141 are male. On the other hand, 53.7% or 121 of the Respondent Consumers are female, while 43.55% or 98 are male and 2.67% are preferred not to mention their gender. From this data, most respondents in the primary sector who use mobile phones for business or sale

transaction are male, while the majority of consumers who purchase or buy online or by mobile phone are female.

2. Productive Sector/Categories

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of

Type	Ferquency	Percentage
Farmers	71	28.86
Fishermen	79	32.11
Miners	28	11.39
Livestock breeder and animal raiser	31	12.6
Forestry	21	8.54
Other	16	6.5
Total	246	100

Types of Primary Sector

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage of respondents by occupation or type of primary sector. Data on occupation were collected to determine whether representation exists in relation to the occupation of the primary sector. This is a major element in determining whether the creation of a mobile application can help them in their work. There are 28.86% or 71 respondents that are farmers, 32.22% or 79 respondents that are fishermen, 11.39% or 28 respondents that are miners while 12.6% or 31 respondents are livestock breeders and animal raisers, there are also 8.54% or 21 respondents whose occupation is forestry, while other primary sector occupation have 6.5% or 16 respondents

3. Age

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms Age

A. Primary Sector		
Type	Ferquency	Percentage
16 years old to 25 years old	20	8.13
26 years old to 35 years old	18	7.32
36 years old to 45 years old	95	38.62
46 years old to 55 years old	93	37.8
56 years old or older	20	8.13
Total	246	100

B. Consumer

Type	Ferquency	Percentage
16 years old to 25 years old	78	34.67
26 years old to 35 years old	83	36.89
36 years old to 45 years old	38	16.89
46 years old to 55 years old	19	8.44
56 years old or older	7	3.11
Total	225	100

Table 3 shows the age-related frequency and percentage of respondents. As far as the primary sector is concerned, between 36 and 45 years of age, 38.62% or 95 of the respondents are in this age group, while 37.8 % or 93 of the respondents are in the age group

46 to 55 years of age. The age group 16 to 25 years of age and 56 years of age or older have a similar number of respondents receiving 8.13% or 20 of the respondents, separately. While the 26-year-old to 35-year-old age group has 7.32% or 18 respondents. The age was included in this study to know their readiness to adopt mobile phone technology as part of their business activities.

On the other hand, most of the respondents belong to the age group 26 years to 35 years with 36.89% or 83 respondents, while 34.67% or 78 respondents belong to the age group 16 years to 25 years. The age group 36 to 45 years of age has 16.89% or 38 respondents, while the age group 46 to 55 years of age has 8.44% or there are 19 respondents, and lastly, the age group 56 years old and older have 3.11% or 7 respondents under this category.

This data shows that most of the primary sector belongs to the older age group, while consumers who are interested in using a mobile app to purchase domestic products belong to the younger age group.

The Survey Questionnaire using the Four-point Likert Scale

In this result discussion, Table 4 was shown to guide the interpretation of the outcome of the assessment of the response of the respondents. The Four-point Likert scale ranging from four as the highest value with the qualitative meaning of "Strongly Agree" to one (1) as the lowest value with the qualitative meaning of "Strongly Disagree" was used to assess the following:

Table 4. Verbal Interpretation using Four Point Likert Scale

Rating Scale	Range	Verbal Descriptions	Verbal Interpretations
4	3.51-4.0	Strongly Agree	The respondents are very much in favor of the statement in question.
3	2.51-3.5	Agree	The respondents are in favor of the statement in question.
2	1.51 – 2.5	Disagree	The respondents are not in favor the statement in question.
1	1.00-1.5	Strongly Disagree	The respondents were extremely disapproved of the statement in question.

Table 5. Summary Result of the Responses of the Respondents
(Primary Sector and Consumer) in the Survey Questionnaire

Please select the phrase / word that best suited to your situation	Mean	Median	VI	Rank
1. You have an android/iOS mobile phone or have the capacity to buy an android/iOS mobile phone	2.29	2	Disagree	13
2. You have an internet connection or wifi connection, which you can access at any time	2.23	2	Disagree	14
3. Transportation groups such as Grab, Lalamove, Bus Terminal, etc. are available for delivery in your area when you purchase online or want some goods to be delivered to someone else.	3.30	3	Agree	10
4. You can pay or receive payment for purchases of goods or products through PayMaya, Paypal, GCash, Western Union, Smart Padala, etc.	3.58	4	Strongly Agree	9
5. You can download any mobile apps such as the Market Mobile App for online shopping to your mobile device	2.97	3	Agree	12
6. Direct sales between local industries and consumers are convenient and easy	3.60	4	Strongly Agree	7
7. Direct sales transactions between the primary sector and customers of local domestic products will motivate and strengthen local industries.	3.65	4	Strongly Agree	3
8. You are willing to sell or purchase domestic goods or locally produced goods on-line using a mobile phone app.	3.58	4	Strongly Agree	9
9. Using mobile software applications such as the Market Mobile App as an online sales platform is a competitive way of dealing with a dynamically changing environment	3.62	4	Strongly Agree	6
10. Mobile apps software is a sustainable strategy to help local industries increase their profits.	3.59	4	Strongly Agree	8
11. You expect the goods/products to be delivered to you to be shipped or received in good quality or of superior value.	3.67	4	Strongly Agree	2
12. There should be terms and conditions of purchase, that stipulate that if the product delivered to the consumer is damaged and if such damage is not the fault of the consumer, you expect it to be replaced or refunded.	3.27	3	Agree	11
13. You expect items or goods to be delivered to you in the same form, size and packaging as shown in the mobile app picture.	3.64	4	Strongly Agree	4
14. Strengthening the promotion and sale of locally produced materials and products produced in the Philippines will contribute to economic growth and sustainable natural resources.	3.67	4	Strongly Agree	2
15. Strengthening domestic sales will help foster partnership, cooperation and local community support.	3.58	4	Strongly Agree	9
16. The Market Mobile App, as a means of selling domestic goods and products, is a timely approach and an innovative strategy in the current situation.	3.63	4	Strongly Agree	5
17. You believe that using the Market Mobile App software will help local industries expand their businesses and increase their revenues.	3.74	4	Strongly Agree	1
TOTAL	3.38	3.59	Strongly Agree	

Table 5 provides a summary of the responses from both the primary sector and the consumer. Most of the questions received a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree". Item 4, which both the primary sector and the consumer have shown that they want to use online payment for their sales transactions; items 6 and 7 that relate to personal perception on direct sales transaction; while items 8, 10 and 17 refers to the use of mobile applications in sales transactions; Items 11 and 13 deal with the individual expectations on the mobile application; while items 9, 14, 15 and 16 shows the impact and benefits of mobile phone applications on the marketing and sale of domestic products.

Although this study received positive responses to the survey, where they "agree" on a number of statements they had responded to, the researcher notes that Items 1 and 2 have received a verbal interpretation of "Disagree" on the question of ownership or possession of mobile phones and access to the Internet. The above results show that the respondents strongly agree with the new mobile technology, but some of them do not have a mobile phone to use or access to the Internet. This is clearly discussed in the "digital-divide" framework that, despite programs and projects implemented by the government or by volunteers for innovation, the lack of the necessary equipment would hinder the effectiveness of this innovation and development effort.

Russell and Steele (2013) noted that the following crucial issues leading to a 'digital divide' should be resolved with the digital revolution: 1) lack of connectivity due to poor communication infrastructure; 2) lack of support for the acquisition or purchase of devices, hardware and internet connections and software; 3) lack of awareness, learning and workshop on digital and technical skills; and 4) lack of exchange of communication services. The framework of 'digital divide' has been classified into three social implications: the first relates to inequalities to access the information technology (IT); the second level is inequalities in the ability to use IT; and the third level deals with inequalities in results (Wei et al., 2011).

Most respondents support the idea of innovation and development in mobile applications because it embodies a holistic approach to rural stable source of livelihoods (Duncombe, 2012; Svensson & Wamala, 2012). Although limited in number, the primary sector respondents were genuinely interested and confident that M-Mobile Application may be used as a rural development tool.

Quantitative findings have shown that primary sectors understand the potential of M-Mobile Application technologies to support livelihood opportunities through continuous interaction, consumer links, cooperation, collaborative effort and partnership, and cost-effective transactions.

The proposed market mobile application creation would represent a significant and revolutionary partnership strategy for the primary sector-consumer (Ps2C) relationship. Mobile phone users and the smartphone technology sector have increased significantly in recent years (Turban, et al. 2018). This current "new normal" transformation situation facing the Philippines reflects a growing desire on the part of consumers to have easy, versatile, portable touch-points to make purchase transactions that are usually based on actual physical shopping in a store in close contact with the people around them. The increased use of self-service technologies (SSTs) by consumers — and, in particular, the use of mobile applications — is a key element contributing to the growth of mobile commerce (Newman et al. 2018)

Synthesis of the results using Triangular Analysis

Figure 12. Triangulation Analysis of the present study for the

Development of Market Mobile Application

Related literature has been reviewed, concepts and principles have been analyzed and adopted in this study as illustrated in Figure 12. The analysis was conducted by reviewing the source of the data for this study, such as the responses of primary sector respondents and consumers.

The researcher analyzes the responses of respondents and the theories, principles and framework used by other researchers, evaluates the current situation of the primary sector in the Philippines as well as the publications and reports of the website documents of the PSA, NEDA, DTI and other Local Government Units. The result confirmed that mobile applications are very helpful in changing the livelihoods of the primary sector, but the government should address their need for mobile phones and Internet access.

The researcher provided the matrix of the different studies (Table 6) and, from this analysis, adopted some of the theories applicable to the study, such as the Expectancy-Value Theory and the Digital Divide.

The research from previous studies as illustrated in Table 6 will strengthen the findings of this study and will help to improve the Market Mobile Application in order to provide the primary sector with a platform for advertising and selling its goods and to make full use of mobile technology by providing them with the means to meet their needs, not just through sales transactions, but also in other fields. This application also includes the

everyday condition, weather reports, news, government initiatives and projects, training opportunities, best practices, chatbox, government policy, rules and regulations, and legislation relevant to their sector. Based on their responses and other research findings, all the items the primary sector needs were incorporated into the creation of a Market Mobile app. The subject matter and the discussions presented above in this study were the result of the review of other studies (Table 6) and this application contained the relevant details required to validate the study outcome.

Table 6. Scoping Review Method and Synthesis of the Results using Triangular Analysis

Author/s	Class of Application	Method	Principles and Theories	Findings
Analiza V. Muñoz (Present study)	Mobile application for sales of domestic products	Empirical Analysis (Four-Point Likert Scale, Scoping Review Method) Triangulation Analysis	Expectancy-Value Motivational Theory Digital Divide Framework	The respondents agree that developing the mobile sales transaction application would allow the primary sector to sell domestic goods, but it is difficult for the primary sector to have a mobile phone that is compatible with the mobile application, as they do not have internet access. Consumer respondents are willing to use the Mobile App to buy domestic goods and help the primary sector to have a stable source of income.
Stephane Boyera (2007)	eService on mobile phones	Literature Review (Comparative Analysis)	Digital Divide	It is structured around three major items: enabling browsing capabilities on existing and future phones for emerging markets, exploring how to build and deploy useful eServices by taking into account human aspects like social and cultural specificities, and building capacities through education for developing countries to develop and deploy their own eServices.
Jan A G M Van Dijk (2006)	Digital access review	Empirical Analysis (Inventory of 5 years digital divide research from 2000-2005)	Digital Divide	The results of digital divide research are classified under four successive types of access: motivational, physical, skills and usage. A shift of attention from physical access to skills and usage is observed. In terms of physical access the divide seems to be closing in the most developed countries, concerning digital skills and the use of applications the divide persists or widens
Mingjung Kim, Jeeyeon Kim, Jeonghye Choi and Minakshi Trivedi (2017)	Mobile shopping application	Exploratory Investigation of Mobile Data and Empirical Analysis	Digital Experience and Mobile Browsing	First, online experience and mobile experience both positively relate to the possession of shopping apps. Second, browsing behavior for non-shopping apps helps understand the possession of shopping apps as it reflects user preferences for acquiring more apps. Third, purchasing decisions are explained by digital experience (i.e., online experience and mobile experience) and browsing information from shopping apps, with other factors being of little predictive value
Richard Boateng, Alemayehu Molla, and Richard Heeks (2008)	e-Commerce	Literature Review (Meta Analysis) 245 articles published between 1993 and 2006	Review the theoretical and conceptual approaches used in e-commerce	The findings indicate that the research area is rapidly growing and relatively well-spread across the assessment of e-commerce potential and its adoption and implementation issues in Developing Economies.
David G. Taylor and Michael Levin (2014)	Mobile application	Mathematical Modelling	mobile phone platform (Android vs Apple iOS)	The analysis finds that the level of interest in a retail app is positively related to the consumer's intention to engage in both purchasing and information-sharing activities. In addition, the recency of the consumer's last visit to the retail store has a moderating effect on both types of activities; the more recent the last visit, the larger the effect-size of interest in the app on intention to share information and make a purchase.
Stella Nathalia Ignacia, Rachel Dyah Wiastuti and Drena Mutiara Lemy (2018)	Restaurant Mobile Application	Mathematical Modelling (Mobile Application Rating Scale (MARS)	Customer purchase	This research reveals that branded mobile application has strong relationship with purchase intention, despite whether people install the mobile application or not. However, purchase intention is likely influenced more by branded mobile application non appuser rather than the apps- user itself. Implication of this study provides recommendations for restaurant business to always maintain and enhance the mobile application quality that are expected to be in line with the growth of restaurant revenue.

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